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Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADHITHYA Sbearing USN 6SU21RD001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAGHA Kbearing USN 6SU21RD002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAGHA Kbearing USN 6SU21RD003has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANANDA LAKSHMI T Sbearing USN 6SU21RD004has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANANDHU K Sbearing USN 6SU21RD005 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms APARNA Kbearing USN 6SU21RD006 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AROMAL SHIBU bearing USN 6SU21RD007 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASWIN BABU P V bearing USN 6SU21RD008 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AYISHA THASHREEFA U C bearing USN 6SU21RD009 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DEVAMRUTHA T V bearing USN 6SU21RD010 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMA bearing USN 6SU21RD011 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMA FIDHA K K bearing USN 6SU21RD012 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FIZA AAMI bearing USN 6SU21RD013 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GRESHMA Rbearing USN 6SU21RD014 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HAIFA IBRAHIM bearing USN 6SU21RD015 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HRIDYA K V bearing USN 6SU21RD016 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUBEENA bearing USN 6SU21RD017 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDANA Kbearing USN 6SU21RD018 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PARVATHY ANI bearing USN 6SU21RD019 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RANTHEEZ MOHAMMED M Tbearing USN 6SU21RD020 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SNEHA V P bearing USN 6SU21RD021 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAMIKA V Mbearing USN 6SU21RD022 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAMSIYA MOL Sbearing USN 6SU21RD024has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHAMEENA Sbearing USN 6SU21RD025 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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